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E-LEARNING IN COST ACCOUNTING: THE SICODINET SPREADSHEET WEBINAR

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INDEX

1. INTRODUCTION	1
2. CHARASTERISTICS OF THE WEBINAR	2
3. STRUCTURE AND CONTENTS OF THE WEBINAR.....	3
4. STUDENTS EVALUATION OF THE WEBINAR.....	5
5. CONCLUSIONS	6
6. REFERENCES	7

KNOWLEDGE AREAS

E-learning, Cost Accounting

ABSTRACT

Spreadsheet is a very useful tool for Cost Accounting, but it is not easy to teach how to use it when the class time or the resources are limited. For solving this problem, a web based seminar (Webinar) has been developed related to the subject Cost Accounting in the University of León. Students can learn about spreadsheet and do practical exercises by accessing to the Internet, what makes easy to learn at their own pace. Moreover, they can raise their doubts and get answers in a forum. This initiative has been held for three years with good students' evaluation.

KEYWORDS

Spreadsheet, Cost Accounting, e-learning, webinar, students' evaluation

1. INTRODUCTION

European Higher Education are going through a new process due to, on one hand, the European Higher Education Area, which means the introduction of some changes in the traditional teaching-learning procedures of some countries because student becomes the leading actor/actress of his/her learning and teacher is only a guide, and, on the other hand, the incorporation and spread of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), which make easy the creation of new learning ways and social communication spaces.

Nowadays there are countless electronic and blended learning experiences in higher education; most of them have been successful and satisfactory for teachers and for students. This work is about an on-line spreadsheet seminar linked to the subject Cost Accounting, an e-learning experience which has been held for three academic years in the University of León, which aim is to teach students how to use Spreadsheet and its application in the previous subject.

2. CHARASTERISTICS OF THE WEBINAR

"Webinar: Spreadsheet as support tool for developing management information" has been held since 2004, so different classes of the subject Cost Accounting have learnt to use this useful tool for three academic years.

Cost Accounting is a compulsory subject of the second course of the Management Degree and the Business Sciences Studies. The aim of this subject is that students learn to calculate and control costs which are relevant in the accounting field, and it also has a complementary aim; acquisition of skills for using spreadsheet to solve cost problems. However, the time class is spending to explain the contents and solve some practical exercises. But it is not possible to solve the exercises in spreadsheet because there are not enough computers and the time is limited. In order to sort out this difficulty, a voluntary seminar was developed some years ago. In the beginning the seminar was given in a computers room and it approximately lasted twenty hours. A teacher shows the main utilities of spreadsheets and students do some exercises for practising during the class time and, when the time class finished, the teachers evaluated them. However, owing to the great number of students and the limited computers, which force to do several groups, it was a very long activity.

In order to get a solution, an e-learning seminar was created three years ago, in 2004. This seminar also tries to show the use of spreadsheet but students can control their own learning. The spreadsheet seminar is developed in a Virtual Learning Space, so-called "Control and Management Information Systems in Telematic Environments, SICODINET" (<http://sicodinet.unileon.es>), which has several courses related to the Cost Accounting profile, as Figure 1 shows. SICODINET has been developed in the Moodle (<http://www.moodle.com>) platform because it is free software which has several operative, technical and legal advantages.

Students can access to the Webinar whenever and wherever they want, read information about spreadsheet which is structured in different lessons and, finally, do practical exercises or tasks which will be sent to the teachers for their evaluation. The Webinar also allows students to learn at their own pace because they can spend more time by studying some utilities that they consider more important or difficult and they advance without waiting for other students or for the teacher, although they have a deadline for sending the practical exercises. Moreover, at the same time they can communicate with their seminar friends, students or teachers, by means of a forum, for raising their doubts or answering other students' questions. Because of this, this category of seminar has numerous advantages:

- Students can connect to the Internet and learn about spreadsheet without being in a classroom with a teacher and other students.
- Students can adapt their training to their own previous knowledge about spreadsheet, so they can build and handle their learning process.

- Students can ask other students or teachers about their doubts in the forum and, if they know the answer, they can help other students.
- A virtual communication space is created because of the students and teachers' participation in the forum, what favours a social and shared learning.
- Teachers can evaluate the practical exercises when students send them, what make easy the individual communication and feed back.
- Students can manage their own training, but teachers also can harmonize all the students' learning process by setting deadlines for practical tasks.

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- Course categories
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Albert Einstein se encontraba en la Universidad realizando un examen de Física. Uno de los alumnos le dijo que había un problema, porque las preguntas que estaba dando eran las mismas del examen del año pasado. "No hay problema", le dijo Einstein. "este año las respuestas ya son otras".

El otro día, al venir para Vegezana, me acerqué a una obra donde tres obreros se encontraban trabajando. Pregunté a uno de ellos: "¿qué está haciendo?", a lo que me respondió: "estoy colocando ladrillos". Pregunté al segundo lo mismo, y me contestó: "estoy

Figure 1. SICODINET VLS Access page

3. STRUCTURE AND CONTENTS OF THE WEBINAR

The spreadsheet Webinar was one of the first initiatives in e-learning holding in the University of León. For its development, different resources of Moodle have been used, but most of students do not have experience in e-learning, so the general working guidelines are showed in a Power Point summary.

The seminar is organized in eight modules. At the beginning, in the first and second seminar, seven of the modules were for general use of spreadsheet and only one was about its specific application in Cost Accounting. However, students ask for other spreadsheet utilities which could be useful in manage and business field. Because of this demand, this year the seminar has, as well as a module for solving cost problems, a module for financial functions and another module for sensitive analysis tools. The seminar still has eight modules but only five are about general use of spreadsheet (some lessons and tasks have been grouped for reducing the number of modules so that the seminar has

more contents). So, the last Webinar, which access page is showed in Figure 2, is structured in the next modules:

- Basic concepts of spreadsheet. Its aim is to have a first contact with spreadsheet: how spreadsheet structure is, inserting data or changing the cells appearance.
- Basic operations. It tries to show how to introduce formulas and functions, using absolute references, ways for copying and pasting, etc.
- Construction of graphics, information presentation and spreadsheet macros. Doing an illustration from spreadsheet information, selecting information for printing or moving to other software and designing macros are the objectives of this module.
- Basic functions. This module tries to describe the general operation of Excel functions and some details of some ones.
- Financial functions. This is a new module which was adding this year. Its aim is to study in depth some functions which are useful in finance field.
- Sensitive analysis tools. It shows how to use some tools, as Solver or Tables, which may be use in order to create different choices for making decisions or optimizing them.
- Aesthetic components of spreadsheet. This is a voluntary module in which students may learn how to improve the appearance of a spreadsheet by introducing control buttons.
- Summary exercises. The aim of this module is to applying the previous knowledge to Cost Accounting practical exercises.

The screenshot shows the Sicedinet Seminar interface. The main content area is titled "Topic outline" and lists three modules:

- 1 **Conceptos fundamentales de una Hoja Electrónica de Cálculo**
 - Introducción
 - Ejercicio de introducción
 - Formato de celdas
 - Formatos
 - Crucigrama
 - Menu de contexto y de edición
- 2 **Operaciones básicas**
 - Operaciones básicas
 - Operaciones básicas
- 3 **Construcción de gráficos, presentación de información e introducción a las macros**
 - Representación gráfica y presentación de información
 - Gráficos
 - Macros
 - Grabación de macros

The right sidebar includes a calendar for February 2007, "Upcoming Events" (stating "There are no upcoming events"), and "Recent Activity".

Figure 2. Webinar access page

Each module has two types of contents, lessons and practical tasks. The lessons have conceptual contents which are useful and outstanding. When

students read the theoretical contents, they can access to the corresponding practical tasks and solving them. They send the tasks when are finished and teachers correct and evaluate them. If there are some mistakes, teacher show them for correcting and students send again the task.

Regarding the length, the seminar starts by early October and ends in December, before Christmas holidays, so students have more than two months for reading the lessons and doing the practical tasks. The seminar has a calendar which shows the sending deadline of the tasks; generally students have seven days for doing two tasks, but it is a flexible time because all the modules are always accessible, so students can make progress and send other tasks which are programmed for later weeks. Because of this fact, it is possible that each student adapts the seminar length to his/her own learning process.

The main advantage of the webinar is the possibility of changing doubts and their solutions by means of a forum. The doubts arisen during the individual study are asked and answered by other students or by the teachers. So, a student may improve his/her own knowledge and help other ones to build their knowledge, by checking his/her learning level.

4. STUDENTS EVALUATION OF THE WEBINAR

The year 2004/2005 was the first time that the Webinar was held, but an attendance seminar in a computers classroom was held simultaneously. However the number of students who chose the Webinar was larger, so, together with the advantages pointed out before, it was another reason for betting on the Webinar.

With regard to the students who passed the seminar, in 2004/2005 the 80% of students who started, finished it, in 2005/2006, the percentage was 68% and in 2006/2007 the 48% of students, so the percentage has been reduced each year. Many students star the seminar but when it makes more difficult, they give up it.

Since 2005/2006 students give their opinion about the seminar by means of an anonymous web questionnaire. It has four parts: general working, methodology, contents and other opinions. So, there are a great number of questions but only some important questions and answers related to e-learning are going to be showed.

All students agree to the forum is "very useful" or "useful", but in 2006/2007 a bigger percentage evaluates it with the best mark (62.79% in 2005/2006 and 69.23% in 2006/2007).

With regard to the students' participation in the forum, in 2005/2006 most of students think it was "poor" (46.51%) and "usual" (41.86%), but in 2006/2007 many more students think it was "usual" (65.38%) and many fewer students

evaluate it as "poor" (26.92%). Only a few think it was "too much" (2.33% in 2005/2006 and 3.85% in 2006/2007).

Regarding the question about the usefulness of other students' answers for solving their individual doubts, the answers are not so unanimous; most of students think that they have solved "some" of their doubts with the forum (65.12% in 2005/2006 and 76.92% in 2006/2007) and few students think that they have solve "almost all" their doubts in the forum (4.65% an 3.85%, respectively), but some ones also think that the forum was not useful for solving their doubts (23.26% in 2005/2006 and 11.54% in 2006/2007) or don't know (6.98% and 7.69%, respectively).

However, most of students agree to the teachers' help for doing the tasks was "enough" (97.67% in 2005/2006 and 88.46% in 2006/2007) and only some ones think it was "poor", although this mark was given by more students in 2006/2007 than in 2005/2006 (2.33% in the first year and 11.54% in the second year).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The changes which are happening in higher education involve a new teaching-learning process because students are going to be more active in the building of their knowledge. Moreover, students have to use CIT, which, at the same time, can develop and improve some skills expected in new higher education.

The Webinar has meant that teachers and students adapt themselves to new learning tools, which at the beginning was a great effort from teachers, who had to use a platform for developing the seminar, design lessons and tasks, etc. Some resources have been re-used, but other ones have been designed again for correcting mistakes and adapting to students, who are more trained in computing. Furthermore, this activity has meant a longer time, not only for designing, but also for checking and evaluating the students' tasks and for answering their doubts.

We are happy with students' interest in the Webinar and over all, with their evaluation because they think that the spreadsheet Webinar is useful for their training.

However, we are concerned about the percentage of students who ends the Webinar because it has been reduced each year. In order to avoid it, we think that students need more support and it would be interesting to have at least a meeting with the students for encouraging them in the middle of the Webinar.

Regarding the students' participation in the forum, we would like to improve it because, although each year they raise and answer more questions due to their better training, it is also expected that they help other ones in their learning process.

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